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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Renewable energy is a growing market with most of its productivity attributed to solar and wind power. Marine renewable energy has been widely associated with tidal power plants, whereas wave energy remains a relatively small market with enormous potential. Many recent designs of wave energy converters (WEC) – such as the MegaRoller concept - were developed for shallow coastal waters. Consequently, optimisation of the design and assessment of potential deployment sites for these WEC greatly depend on a detailed understanding of the nearshore wave field in dependence of the characteristics of incoming swells, tide, and local bathymetry.

To understand the dynamic coastal system, researchers and engineers show an increasing interest in phase-resolving numerical models. Especially, models built around Boussinesq-type equations have developed into powerful tools for coastal engineering as well as for assessment studies of coastal hazards and marine renewable energy.

This theory and user manual describes the numerical code BOSZ (Boussinesq Ocean & Surf Zone model) for the solution of a set of Boussinesq-type equations and helps future users to work through particular examples and benchmarks to become familiar with the code. The model provides accurate and robust solutions in a reasonable amount of time for a wide range of nearshore wave processes, which include wave propagation, transformation, breaking and run-up on land. Due to the phase resolving nature of the model, secondary processes such as wave set-up, recirculation, and generation of infra-gravity waves are well captured within the solution structure. The BOSZ model can be used to facilitate WEC designs and to assess potential deployment sites. In particular, and as part of the MegaRoller project, the BOSZ model will support the characterisation of WEC deployment site, which can inform the definition of the critical design situations to consider as part of the design process (e.g. by defining normal and extreme sea states), or the definition of a wave-by-wave prediction of the wavefield approaching the device, enabling a real-time adjustment of the control algorithm to optimise the power-take off (PTO).

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope of the Document

Many recent designs of wave energy converters (WEC) - such as the WaveRoller concept - are being developed for shallow coastal waters. Consequently, optimisation of the design and selection of potential deployment sites for these WEC greatly depends on a detailed understanding of the nearshore wave field, considering e.g. the incoming swells, tide, and local bathymetry effects. To understand the dynamic coastal system, researchers and engineers show an increasing interest in phase-resolving numerical models. Especially, models built around Boussinesq-type equations have developed into powerful tools for coastal engineering as well as for assessment studies of coastal hazards and marine renewable energy.

Furthermore, in the context of WEC, the depth-integrated Boussinesq-type models can yield a wave-by-wave prediction of the wavefield approaching the device, enabling a real-time adjustment of the control algorithm to optimise the power-take off (PTO).

Therefore, and as part of the MegaRoller project, a Boussinesq model, called the Boussinesq Ocean and Surf Zone (BOSZ), was developed for two purposes: first, to characterise accurately the nearshore wave field for site selection and design optimisation, and second, to be used in connection with an Echo State Model to compute expected wave heights and periods in real time and inform the wave-by-wave damping control strategy.

The benefit of the BOSZ model is its ability to describe a fully developed sea state along a 1D transect or in the 2D horizontal plane. The model computes wave-by-wave of a wide range of sea states commonly encountered in the nearshore domain around the deployment site of the WaveRoller. These wave conditions vary between long-period energetic open ocean swells and local wind waves. The wavemaker of the BOSZ model was particularly developed to generate waves from all directions allowing a full representation of the wave field at the site. In contrast to other models of similar type, the BOSZ code can compute waves from opposing directions. With focus on the particular WaveRoller site, this could include a long-period swell from the Southwest paired with a short-period wind swell from the North or vice versa.

In addition, it is possible to implement sink terms for representation of the energy extraction by the WaveRoller device. Though the model computes the wave field in the 2D horizontal plane through depth-integration of the full 3D problem, it is still possible to mimic the energy extraction of a WEC from an individual wave through a sink term, which works like a partially porous wall. The sink absorbs energy from the sea state and consequently leads to a modification of the wave field surrounding the WEC. Changes in wave setup and infra-gravity energy then cause changes in recirculation currents, which can affect the waves in relatively far distance from the actual WEC site.

The BOSZ model runs very fast in 1D and therefore is a suitable support tool for an Echo State model by computing variations in the sea state in real-time and thus enabling design and performance optimizations of the WaveRoller's control system.

Following this introduction (Section 1), the document outlines a detailed description of the theoretical governing equations and the model's numerical solution (Section 2) including a flowchart of the code's structure. Finally, Section 3 stands as a user manual, in the form of a benchmark test problem that illustrates the model's setup and performance.

1.2 Acceptance Criteria

This document adheres to the description of the deliverable provided in the Grant Agreement:

“Contain sufficient detail that a new user of the software can implement and use the software. The process is defined in a flow chart or similar and the theory behind the software will be adequately described”.

2 THEORY

2.1 Notation and Definition of Variables

2.1.1 Convention

Unless otherwise stated in the text, the following points should be considered throughout this report:

- Grid directions: x is positive from offshore boundary (left) to the shore (right). y is positive from bottom of matrix to top of matrix. z is positive from initial water level upwards and negative downwards.
- Sub-indices of variables i and j indicate cell coordinates such as $u_{i,j}$ or $u_{i+1,j-1}$. Sub-indices of variables x, y, z and t denote derivatives (e.g. u_x). The derivative applies only to the first variable to their left unless grouping is used (e.g. hu_x is the product of h and the x -derivative of u , while $[hu]_x$ is the derivative of the product hu .)
- Super-indices of the variable n such as H^n or H^{n+1} indicate time steps.
- Super-indices L and R indicate the values to the left and right of a cell interface (e.g. η^L)

2.1.2 Variables

The following variables are used throughout this report (see also Figure 2.1):

- g : earth's gravity, set to 9.81 m/s^2 .
- η : free surface [m] with respect to initial water level. The initial water level is usually defined to be zero, i.e. the zero contour of the bathymetry. However, it is possible to offset the initial still water level to a value other than zero (positive or negative to e.g. reflect a tidal stage).
- h : distance from initial water level [m] to the ground surface (also known as bathymetry). It is positive downwards with a maximum at the bottom. The topography is negative.
- ζ : water level [m] different from still water level (zero contour of bathymetry).
- $H = h + \eta + \zeta$: total water depth [m] (always positive).
- Reference water depth, at which the flow velocity is computed: (z_α, x, y) set as $-0.531h$.
- u : particle velocity [m/s] in the x -direction. It is called "particle velocity", since it represents the speed of movement of a fluid particle - in contrast to the wave celerity which represents the speed of the wave envelope.
- v : particle velocity [m/s] in the y -direction (similar to hu).
- w : particle velocity [m/s] in the z -direction. This velocity is not directly solved for because of the depth-integrated nature of the Boussinesq-type equation. However, w can be computed from the prescribed quadratic velocity profile of the horizontal flow velocities.

Figure 2.1: Definition sketch with variables.

2.2 Governing Equations

There exist multiple forms of Boussinesq-type equations to date. These equations have one common property: they all contain the set of Nonlinear Shallow Water (NSW) equations as a subset. This set of NSW is well known in classic river and tsunami flood modelling as the hyperbolic structure of the equations allows for discontinuous solutions and computations of wet-dry interfaces typically present under flooding and wave run-up scenarios. However, and also commonly known, the NSW equations assume a fully hydrostatic pressure distribution throughout the water column and are therefore not fully applicable to nearshore waves where frequency dispersion plays an important role.

The basic idea behind the BOSZ model is the combination of shock-capturing capabilities from the conserved NSW equations with the dispersive properties of conventional Boussinesq-type equations to provide an accurate and stable solution of wave-by-wave propagation, transformation, breaking, and runup. Boussinesq-type equations always benefit from the presence of the classic Shallow Water Equations as a subset that essentially lead to the computation of the hydrostatic pressure in combination with additional terms accounting for pressure correction due to frequency dispersion. In most situations, the hydrostatic pressure is the dominant component, i.e. This enables the model to handle short (dispersive) waves and transitions between sub- and supercritical flow (wave breaking).

2.2.1 Nwogu's Equations

The present phase-resolving depth-integrated numerical model is based on a conserved variable formulation of equations by [Nwogu, 1993]. Contrary to the NSW equations, Boussinesq equations naturally include dispersion terms to account for the non-hydrostatic pressure effects of periodic waves. To account for frequency dispersion, [Nwogu, 1993] expressed the vertical gradient of the horizontal velocity at an arbitrary depth z_α through a truncated Taylor series expansion in combination with the irrotationality condition $u_z = w_x$. This allows for an approximation of the vertical variation of the horizontal velocity components in terms of only the horizontal velocity components at z_α . The third momentum equation in z-direction vanishes from depth integration and a pseudo 3D solution is obtained in the 2D horizontal plane. The set of equations, expressed in conservative form, consists of a continuity equation and two momentum equations in the x and y-directions. In case of a 1D computation along a transect or bathymetric profile, only the terms in x-direction are retained.

The long-established equations by [Nwogu, 1993] contain a continuity equation and two momentum equation. H is the total water depth, η the free surface elevation, and (u, v) the horizontal flow velocities in x and y directions (see also Figure 2.1). Considering a stationary bathymetry (i.e. $h_t = 0$), based on the fundamental assumptions of small amplitude and long period waves, the original [Nwogu, 1993] in vector notation are:

$$\eta_t + \nabla[(h + \eta)U] + \nabla \cdot \left\{ \left(\frac{z_\alpha^2}{2} - \frac{h^2}{6} \right) h \nabla(\nabla \cdot U) + \left(z_\alpha + \frac{h}{2} \right) h \nabla[\nabla \cdot (hU)] \right\} = 0 \quad [\text{Eq. 1}]$$

$$U_t + U(\nabla \cdot U) + g \nabla \eta + \left\{ \frac{z_\alpha^2}{2} \nabla(\nabla \cdot U) + z_\alpha \nabla[\nabla \cdot (hU)] \right\}_t = 0 \quad [\text{Eq. 2}]$$

Based on the formulation of the equation, the velocity profile for the x and y velocity components are defined as:

$$u_z = u_{z_\alpha} + \frac{1}{2}(z_\alpha^2 - z^2) \left[(u_{z_\alpha})_{xx} + (v_{z_\alpha})_{xy} \right] + (z_\alpha - z) \left[(hu_{z_\alpha})_{xx} + (hv_{z_\alpha})_{xy} \right] \quad [\text{Eq. 3}]$$

$$v_z = v_{z_\alpha} + \frac{1}{2}(z_\alpha^2 - z^2) \left[(u_{z_\alpha})_{xy} + (v_{z_\alpha})_{yy} \right] + (z_\alpha - z) \left[(hu_{z_\alpha})_{xy} + (hv_{z_\alpha})_{yy} \right] \quad [\text{Eq. 4}]$$

[Eq. 3] and [Eq. 4] offer the possibility to recompute the horizontal particle velocities at any vertical position across the water column. Although the quadratic distribution is not always fully applicable, it is in general closer to reality than only a hydrostatic assumption with no variation in pressure at all. The reference depth z is the vertical position within the still water column at which the velocities are evaluated (orange dot in Figure 2.1). It is just below mid depth and varies linearly with the bathymetry. While the bathymetry is positive downwards, z is its negative counterpart, i.e. for the velocity at the seabed $z = h$ and at the free surface $z = 0$.

The set of equations agrees well with the Airy theory in terms of its dispersion properties $kh < \pi$ or a little beyond. This means that the model can generally be used for nearshore waves where the water depth is shallower than half the wavelength. For $kh > \pi$ the dispersion error increases, which causes an overestimation of the wavelength in deep water typical for most equations of this type. The value of z_α can be adjusted for an optimal compromise between linear dispersion and shoaling properties.

Theoretically, variations of z_α could lead to a near perfect agreement with Airy wave theory over a wide range of kh -values if the wave conditions were known in advance. In reality, this is hardly possible as the instantaneous free surface elevation is usually composed of multiple individual waves typical for a developed sea state. Instead, the goal is to find an optimized overall agreement with a universal fixed value of z_α for each grid cell, the reference depth z_α , defined in [Nwogu, 1993] as a fixed proportion of the local water depth with a position near mid depth, z_α .

Since the choice of z_α affects both linear and nonlinear wave components, it is important to find the best match between frequency dispersion and shoaling properties. So far, most studies have used values around $z_\alpha = -0.531 \cdot h$ as initially proposed by [Nwogu, 1993] and this is also used here. Figure 2.2 shows the error in the linear phase velocity in the original Peregrine system [Peregrine, 1967] and the Nwogu system.

Figure 2.2: Wave celerity of [Nwogu, 1993] equations in comparison with the classical Boussinesq equations [Peregrine, 1967].

2.2.2 Modified Nwogu’s Equations in Conservative Variables

Depth-integrated equations, which include non-hydrostatic properties, such as Boussinesq-type formulations were developed to handle nearshore processes in the subcritical as well as the supercritical regime. [Toro, 2001] demonstrated that the classical shallow water equations cater to Finite Volume schemes, if the formulation is based on conserved form. In the model presented in this report, this concept was adopted and the transported variables of the equations of [Nwogu, 1993] are expressed as conserved variables. The continuity equation can be readily expressed in terms of the total depth H instead of η . In differential form, this leads to:

$$H_t + (Hu)_x + (Hv)_y + \Psi_C + \Psi_{wm} = 0 \quad [\text{Eq. 5}]$$

Where

$$\Psi_C = \left[\left(\frac{z_\alpha^2}{2} - \frac{h^2}{6} \right) h(u_{xx} + v_{xy}) + \left(z_\alpha + \frac{h}{2} \right) h \left((hu)_{xx} + (hv)_{xy} \right) \right]_x + \left[\left(\frac{z_\alpha^2}{2} - \frac{h^2}{6} \right) h(u_{xy} + v_{yy}) + \left(z_\alpha + \frac{h}{2} \right) h \left((hu)_{xy} + (hv)_{yy} \right) \right]_y \quad [\text{Eq. 6}]$$

Here, Ψ_{wm} is a mass source term for the generation of spectral waves. This term is not part of the original equations by [Nwogu, 1993].

The momentum equations with conserved variables, Hu and Hv arise from [Eq. 2] after pre-multiplication with H in combination with the continuity equation [Eq. 1], which is pre-multiplied by u and v respectively. Since both H as well as u, v are time-dependent variables, the temporal derivative does not only apply to u, v , but also to H . The conserved variable formulation changes the local acceleration terms from the original definition in [Nwogu, 1993] u_t to $(Hu)_t$ and from v_t to $(Hv)_t$.

The momentum equations in conserved variables are denoted as:

$$(Hu)_t + (Hu^2)_y + (Huv)_y + Hg\eta_x + H \frac{z_\alpha^2}{2} [u_{xxt} + v_{xyt}] + Hz_\alpha [(hu_t)_{xx} + (hv_t)_{xy}] + u\Psi_C + \tau_1 = 0 \quad [\text{Eq. 7}]$$

$$(Hv)_t + (Hv^2)_y + (Huv)_x + Hg\eta_y + H \frac{z_\alpha^2}{2} [v_{yyt} + u_{xyt}] + Hz_\alpha [(hv_t)_{yy} + (hu_t)_{xy}] + v\Psi_C + \tau_2 = 0 \quad [\text{Eq. 8}]$$

[Eq. 7] and [Eq. 8] lead to the conserved variable formulation where momentum is transported in time instead of only particle speed, which is not a conserved property. This formulation holds for sub- and supercritical flows with Froude number > 1 . It should be noted that the hydrostatic NSW equations in conserved variable form are a complete subset of this Boussinesq-type equation. The last terms in both momentum equations account for bottom friction drag where:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_1 &= gn^2 H^{(-2/3)} u \sqrt{(u^2 + v^2)} \\ \tau_2 &= gn^2 H^{(-2/3)} v \sqrt{(u^2 + v^2)} \end{aligned} \quad [\text{Eq. 9}]$$

where n is the Manning roughness coefficient with units $[s/m^{1/3}]$. The Manning n represents the surface property of the sea floor or the terrain with typical values < 0.04 .

2.2.3 Nonlinear Effects (Wave Setup, Surfbeat)

For monochromatic waves under idealized laboratory conditions, the mean water level nearshore approaches a steady equilibrium known as wave setup. In nature, wind-generated swells are composed of a variation of waves with different frequencies (spectrum) that form wave groups due to the dispersion relation. In the surf zone, these wave groups lead to sets of breaking waves and subsequently to pulses of radiation stress (surf beat). Hence, temporal fluctuations of the wave setup are the consequence. This is known as surf beat. In addition, other long-period oscillations can occur from interactions with the local bathymetry. Examples are trapped waves and resonances over shallow shoals, reef patches, or in embayment.

All these long waves are resulting from second-order effects of the incoming swell waves and exhibit substantial dynamics. Under extreme conditions, the surf beat can even shoal across the runup zone and steepen into a destructive bore, which has features of a tsunami wave. The governing equations of Boussinesq-type and other non-hydrostatic equations in conjunction with a suitable numerical scheme can compute wave setup, surf beat, and other infra-gravity (IG) motions.

The variations of the water level nearshore can be seen as a change of the local water depth over time that is not associated with each individual wave but rather connected to the wave group, which has a major influence on the water level in the surf zone. In the swash zone, where the water depth tends to zero, the fluctuations of the water table are largest. i.e. the surf beat is often of the same order of magnitude as the local water depth. With reference to the sensitivity of the z_α -value above, it becomes obvious that any offset from the optimum level will lead to an adverse effect of dispersion and nonlinear properties.

2.3 Numerical Solution

The present Boussinesq-type formulation, with the NSW equations as subset, caters to solutions based on conservative numerical methods. As in previous studies, BOSZ uses a combination of a Finite Volume scheme for the hydrostatic parts of the equations and a central differential Finite Difference scheme for the nonhydrostatic pressure correction terms. The Finite Volume scheme solves for the spatial gradients of the flux and bed slope terms based of a solution from the Harten–Lax–van Leer Contact (HLLC) approximate Riemann solver at all cell interfaces.

A two-dimensional limiting reconstruction method presented in Kim et al. (2008) provides the input variables for the Riemann solution at all sides of the grid cells. The User has the option to use a 2nd, 3rd, 4th, or 5th-order reconstruction approach. The results from the 4th and 5th-order schemes are nearly identical. The higher-order methods reduce numerical diffusion.

2.3.1 Conserved Vector Formulation

The equations can be cast in conservative vector form as: $U_t + F(U)_x + G(U)_y + S(U) = 0$, where the vectors of the continuity equation and the two momentum equation can be expanded as:

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{bmatrix} H \\ P \\ Q \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{U}) = \begin{bmatrix} Hu \\ Hu^2 + \frac{1}{2}g\eta^2 + g\eta h \\ Huv \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{U}) = \begin{bmatrix} Hv \\ Hvu \\ Hv^2 + \frac{1}{2}g\eta^2 + g\eta h \end{bmatrix} \quad [\text{Eq. 10}]$$

The variables $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{U})$ and $\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{U})$ contain the homogeneous portion of the NSW equations with expanded surface gradient terms that are solved with a Finite Volume scheme. The local acceleration and source terms are part of the Finite Difference scheme and given as:

$$\mathbf{S}(\mathbf{U}) = \begin{bmatrix} \psi_C + \psi_{wm} \\ -g\eta h_x + u\psi_C - H_t\psi_P - \psi_{P2} + H\tau_1 - \psi_{B1} \\ -g\eta h_y + v\psi_C - H_t\psi_Q - \psi_{Q2} + H\tau_2 - \psi_{B2} \end{bmatrix} \quad [\text{Eq. 11}]$$

The additional term in the continuity equation accounts for the generation of single monochromatic waves and the superposition of multiple individual waves in form of a directional spectrum. ψ_{wm} is adding and subtracting mass, however the total mass over one wave cycle is not changed as crest and trough dislocate an identical volume. The term is given as:

$$\psi_{wm_{i,j}} = \sum_{i=1}^{M_\omega} \sum_{j=1}^{M_\theta} a_{ij} \cos [k_i (y \cos\theta_j) - \omega_i t + \phi_{ij}] \quad [\text{Eq. 12}]$$

where ϕ_{ij} is the random wave phase and M_ω and M_θ denote the numbers of frequency and direction bins the wave spectrum is composed of. The source strength a_{ij} is calculated according to [Wei, 1999]. Figure 2.3 provides an example of wave spectrum with multiple frequencies and directions. The wavemaker considers each bin in frequency and direction as one individual monochromatic wave with a random phase. In 1D, the binning would only occur along the frequency axis and all directional bins would be collapsed into one bin (no directionality).

Figure 2.3: Directional wave spectrum as commonly provided by wave buoys or spectral models.

BOSZ includes total variation diminishing (TVD) versions of the 2nd, 3rd and 4th-order Runge-Kutta time integration methods based on [Eq. 3] (see [Gottlieb & Shu, 1998])[Gottlieb & Shu, 1998]. These schemes favour the use of a dynamically changing time step based on the overall flow field, since higher-order accuracy is achieved throughout multiple evaluations of the equation per time step instead of through storage of previous solutions.

The evolution variables P and Q with combined flux and dispersion terms in [Eq. 10] form tridiagonal linear systems of equations, which can be solved for the horizontal flow velocities u and v through a lower-upper (LU) decomposition with data dependency in either the x or the y direction. This facilitates parallel computation as no iterative procedure is required. The upper, lower, and diagonal vectors of the sparse matrices can be pre-factored in the beginning of the computation and only have to be multiplied by a changing H in each Runge-Kutta step throughout the time integration procedure. P and Q are evolved in time as evolution variables and depend only on variations of u and v respectively. The other variables in P and Q are not time dependent.

By approximating:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P &= H u_{i,j} + \frac{z_\alpha^2}{2} [H u_{xx}] + z_\alpha [H (hu)_{xx}] \\
 &\approx H_{i,j} u_{i,j} + \left(\frac{z_\alpha^2}{2}\right)_{i,j} \left[H_{i,j} \frac{u_{i+1} - 2u_i + u_{i-1}}{2} \right] + (z_\alpha)_{i,j} \left[H_{i,j} \frac{(hu)_{i+1} - 2(hu)_i + (hu)_{i-1}}{2} \right]
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{Eq. 13}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q &= H v + \frac{z_\alpha^2}{2} [H v_{yy}] + z_\alpha [H (hv)_{yy}] \\
 &\approx H_{i,j} v_{i,j} + \left(\frac{z_\alpha^2}{2}\right)_{i,j} \left[H_{i,j} \frac{v_{j+1} - 2v_j + v_{j-1}}{2} \right] + (z_\alpha)_{i,j} \left[H_{i,j} \frac{(hv)_{j+1} - 2(hv)_j + (hv)_{j-1}}{2} \right]
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{Eq. 14}$$

Variables u and v can be found at the next time step through solution of the two linear systems of equations. The two systems are independent of each other and only depend on x and y derivatives

respectively. [Eq. 13] and [Eq. 14] leads to sequential 1D data dependencies, which facilitate the parallelization structure of the algorithm for efficient computations on super computers.

In addition, the momentum equations contain non-hydrostatic parts from the orthogonal velocity components with cross-space and time derivatives (see [Eq. 11]) that are treated separately. The xyt cross terms are:

$$(\Psi)_{P2} = \frac{z_\alpha^2}{2} (Hv)_{xyt} + z_\alpha (Hhv)_{xyt} \quad [\text{Eq. 15}]$$

$$(\Psi)_{Q2} = \frac{z_\alpha^2}{2} (Hu)_{xyt} + z_\alpha (Hhu)_{xyt} \quad [\text{Eq. 16}]$$

The time derivative is approximated with first-order upwinding based on the present and previous solution of u and v , respectively. Here, the variable H is not part of the time derivative, because [Eq. 7] and [Eq. 8] involve only the x - and y -components as conserved variables. The cross- xyt terms do not involve combined $(Hu)_t$ and $(Hv)_t$ terms.

2.3.2 Flux Calculation

2.3.2.1 Riemann Solution

The Riemann solution is a common way of calculating the advective terms (fluxes) of the NSW equations. These terms are present in $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{U})$ and $\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{U})$ of [Eq. 10]. The Riemann solution is the solution to a discontinuity problem, which could potentially be present along any of the cell interfaces in the numerical domain.

A Riemann problem is defined as the initial value problem (IVP) constituted by a system of partial differential equations (in this case, the NSW equations) and a two-state discontinuous initial value. The Riemann solution employed in this model is the Harten-Lax-vanLeer scheme for contact discontinuities (HLLC). This scheme has been widely used in the water wave community due to its robustness and accuracy. However, it comes with the disadvantage of being slightly diffusive, which for long wave problems is less of an issue. The drawback becomes more pronounced with shorter waves as it is the case for swell waves. Especially in the nearshore wave field, swell waves gain steepness, and the numerical diffusivity of the conventional Riemann scheme can quickly lead to a reduction in wave amplitude after multiple wave cycles.

2.3.2.2 Finite Difference Upwind Scheme

The Riemann solver provides a robust and well-balanced scheme for flows over irregular terrain. The Riemann solver scheme was mainly developed for shock-capturing purposes, i.e. to compute flow discontinuities. However, most of the computational domain of a nearshore wave model requires the computation of smooth solutions and not only breaking waves. It is important to keep in mind that the individual waves first have to propagate towards the shore before they break and run up on the beach. This propagation process requires the computation of several wave cycles with ideally minimal loss of energy due to numerical diffusion.

Noting that numerical diffusion adds to numerical stability, a reasonable compromise between low diffusivity and stability can be found through computing the flux terms with a second-order upwind scheme and then switch to the Riemann solution near the breaking point.

The difference between the Riemann solution and an upwind scheme become evident in case of a wave spectrum propagated through a long channel. The input spectrum is a TMA spectrum of $H_s = 2\text{m}$ and $T_p =$

15s propagated for 2h along a 25km channel. Three observation points at 2km, 12km, and 22km show the spectral evolution.

The left panel of Figure 2.4 below illustrates the disadvantages of flux computations based on Riemann solutions: Numerical diffusion. The problem becomes evident for oscillatory wave motion over large distances with relatively coarse grid spacing. The right panel, in contrast, shows the same wave evolution computed with a second-order upwind scheme with only minimal numerical diffusion.

Figure 2.4: Power spectral density: Power spectral density at three positions in a long channel of 50m depth and with a grid spacing of $\Delta x = 10m$ and no friction. The significant wave height of the TMA input spectrum is 2m with 15s peak period.

The BOSZ code combines the Riemann solution and the upwind flux scheme by simply computing the flux terms in two ways. A threshold of $2 \cdot H_s$ ensures that the Riemann solution is applied to all cells where the water depth is shallower than twice the significant wave height. Typically, it can be considered that no waves will break in water depth of twice the significant wave height. The waves then travel up to close to the breaking point in a relatively non-diffusive fashion and once the steepness increases and waves break, the Riemann scheme – albeit its slightly higher diffusivity – ensures stable and accurate solutions of breaking waves and run-up.

2.3.3 Time Integration

The BOSZ code offers 2nd, 3rd, and 4th order time integration options based on Runge-Kutta schemes. The 2nd order scheme offers the best compromise between numerical cost and accuracy. Since, Runge-Kutta schemes belong to the family of multistep methods, higher order accuracy is obtained through re-evaluation of the solution. This process usually increases the computational load near linearly, i.e. the 4th order solution takes about twice the time as the 2nd order solution.

For a generic variable u this method is a two-step predictor-corrector process that takes the form:

$$u^{n+1} = u^n + \Delta t F(u^n) \tag{Eq. 17}$$

$$u^{n+1} = u^n + \Delta t F(u^n) \tag{Eq. 18}$$

where u^{n+1} is the variation of u computed in the predictor step and u^{n+1} the variation of u computed in the corrector step.

2.3.4 Boundary Conditions

In the model presented in this report, reflective and absorbing boundary conditions are implemented by means of ghost cells. Ghost cells are auxiliary cells, for which the computation is performed but whose

value is not intended to be used for the results. Reflective boundaries are easily obtained by inverting the sign of the flow speed variables (u in x-direction and v in y-direction).

Absorbing boundary conditions can be either based on the radiation condition for hydrostatic flows or sponge layers. The radiation condition has the advantage that it can be imposed directly on the boundary based on the relation $\eta = -u\sqrt{H/g}$ on the left side and $\eta = u\sqrt{H/g}$ on the right side in x-direction. The conditions in y-direction are similar with v instead of u being used.

The other option of absorbing boundary conditions is based on the concept of sponge layers. Sponge layers are cosine functions imposed on the flux terms to transition the computed values to zero at the boundaries. Sponge layers are very efficient and almost not reflective, though they require additional computation. The width of the sponge layer is computed from the wavelength corresponding to the peak period in a wave spectrum. To reduce the computational load, a maximum of 50 cells is hard coded in the model. However, the user can set the amount of sponge layer cells manually. Attention should be paid to the computational area under the influence of the sponge layer, since the solution from the sponge layer cells does not represent the solution of the water wave problem but instead rather reflects some dead-weight necessary to mimic open ocean boundaries.

2.3.5 Applicable Range of Water Depth to Wavelength

Figure 2.2 shows that the dispersion properties of Boussinesq-type equations depend on the ratio of wavelength to water depth or simply the kh -value. Figure 2.5 illustrates the error in wavelength with respect to wave period for a selected water depth between 25m and 200m. The dashed black line denotes the reference solution from Airy wave theory, which serves as reference. Overall, short waves ($L/h < 1$, small ratio of wavelength to water depth) are barely affected by the local water depth, whereas shallow water conditions ($L/h > 1$) result in a reduction of wavelength. Nwogu's equation shows an increasing overestimation of the wavelength for $kh > \pi$ (area to the left of the green line).

Linear wave theory shows a clear dependence of the wavelength to the local water depth. The longer the wave or the higher the period, the earlier the wavelength is affected by the water depth ($\tanh(kh)$ -term in the dispersion relation). For the shown examples of water depth starting with 25m, the wavelength remains nearly unaffected for wave periods shorter than 7s.

Boussinesq approximations exhibit phase speed errors depending on the kh -value. In general, for a given water depth and wavelength (kh) the dispersion properties show a positive error.

As an example, the thin gray lines indicate the wavelengths of an 8s wave in different water depths. Linear wave theory shows that a wave of 8s period will be almost 100m long if the water depth is deeper than 50m. In 25m water depth, the wave will be slightly shorter.

With [Nwogu, 1993] Boussinesq approximation however, the 8s wave will be about 105m long in 50m water depth and even 123m long in water of 100m depth. This corresponds to the expected errors at $kh = \pi$ and $kh = 2\pi$. To avoid excessively large errors in phase speed, input wave spectra should be truncated between $kh = \pi$ and $kh = 2\pi$. These limits are marked by the green and red lines for each of the selected water depths.

For example, a spectrum truncated at $kh = \pi$ with an offshore water depth of 50m will include wave periods longer than 8s. Shorter waves are considered as the "high-frequency" tail and cropped. The energy from the tail will be redistributed over the remaining spectrum. If the water depth was 100m and $kh = 2\pi$ is chosen as threshold, then the shortest wave period will be about 7s. This wave is roughly 1s

shorter than it should be because of the error in celerity, which over-predicts the wavelength. Remember that, according to Airy wave theory, a wave of 100m length should have a period of 8s if the water depth is deeper than 50m. (all numbers are approximate values).

Figure 2.5: Error in wavelength (L) from the linearized Nwogu’s equation (with $\alpha = -0.531h$) in comparison to Airy wave theory for selected water depths (h).

2.3.6 Wave Breaking

Wave breaking in Boussinesq-type models has been an open debate for many years. As the governing equations are not catering to flow discontinuities due to their parabolic structure, several possibilities exist to make the equations hold for such regimes. It is important to notice why some Boussinesq equations have problems with breaking waves, flow discontinuities and supercritical flows. Based on the fundamental characteristics of the equations expressed with conventional physical variables (η, u, v) is the limitation of being restricted to subcritical flows. As soon as $Fr > 1$, physical variables are unable to correctly calculate the momentum transfer, since a shock solution always requires both mass and momentum to be transported together. With only particle speed, which is not a conserved quantity, as the time dependent variable in the momentum equations, the phase speed will be underestimated and the height of the free surface will consequently be overestimated because mass is still conserved via continuity. Now, that is exactly the reason BOSZ is based on conserved variables. This structure allows for supercritical flows on-the-fly and does not require tracking or readjustment of the breaking waves. The only thing that needs to be taken care of is the excessive contribution of the dispersion terms, which can grow to unnaturally large quantities along the steep wave faces. With a missing diffusion or turbulence term, the grow of dispersion at the wave face is a logical consequence of the balancing between amplitude dispersion (nonlinear effects) and frequency dispersion. Although this is technically not wrong, for numerical implementations, solutions that do not create sources for instabilities and that enable a smooth transition between sub- and supercritical flows are sought for.

One way is the addition of eddy diffusivity terms to the momentum equations that buffer the excessive growth along the wave face. Another approach is focusing on eliminating the source of the problem, which is the excessive dispersion quantity and to make use of the underlying NSW equations, which is applicable to handle wave breaking by describing the overturning wave as a discontinuity/bore.

2.3.6.1 Deactivation of Dispersion Based on Momentum Gradient

An easy way to eliminate the possibility of instabilities near the wave front is ignoring dispersion locally once a threshold in the momentum gradient is exceeded. Depth-integrated models do not describe overturning of the free surface and thus cannot fully reproduce the wave breaking processes. The use of conserved variables in the present governing equations allows approximation of breaking waves as discontinuous flows. Even though the flow is flux-dominated, the governing equations balance shock-related amplitude dispersion with frequency dispersion. This might lead to a local anomaly that can result in numerical instability depending on the order of the dispersion terms, the numerical scheme, and most important, the grid size. BOSZ considers an approach to deactivate the dispersion terms to allow the Riemann solver to describe the breaking wave as a bore or hydraulic jump. Dispersion is deactivated in every cell where the following criterion hold:

$$\begin{aligned} |(Hu)_x| &> B\sqrt{gH} \\ |(Hv)_y| &> B\sqrt{gH} \end{aligned} \quad [\text{Eq. 19}]$$

where $B = 0.5$, based on comparison with experimental data.

2.3.6.2 Deactivation of Dispersion Based on Free-Surface Froude-Number

Here, a new idea on how to address the potentially arising instabilities is introduced. It is a purely numerical treatment under the assumption that dispersion should be maintained wherever possible. The strategy is based on the free surface Froude-Number, which can be determined from the free surface flow velocities. The governing equations allow for calculation of the flow velocity at any position in the water column based on the horizontal velocities and under the assumption of a pre-described quadratic velocity profile as in [Eq. 3], where $z = \eta$.

For $Fr > 1$, the flow becomes supercritical and undular bores can develop. Above $Fr = 0.85-1.0$, hydraulic jumps form and the waves are clearly breaking. Let's define C_{B1} as the limit. If the free surface Froude-Number exceeds C_{B1} , the dispersion terms are completely ignored. This method, however, needs more testing. The computation of the free surface Froude number from the Taylor series approximation involves 2nd-order derivatives, which tend to numerical instabilities over irregular terrain and for irregular wave fields. The horizontal velocities obtained directly at z_α are therefore used at the free surface instead. The onset value C_{B1} has to be chosen slightly lower to account for the lower velocity around mid-depth compared to the free surface.

2.3.6.3 Deactivation of Dispersion Based on Water Depth to Wave Height Ratio

From linear wave theory, waves are understood to tend to break, if the local wave height is larger than 78% of the local water depth. This criterion can be used to deactivate dispersion in the same way as for the other two methods above. Though it is relatively easy to define a wave crest to water depth ratio, it is difficult to know the full height in comparison to the water depth unless a complicated tracking algorithm is employed (particularly difficult in 2D). The threshold of $a/h > 0.78$ should therefore be used with caution because a is measured from crest to trough. Nevertheless, it is possible to define the ratio by a lower value, e.g. 0.6, to account for some wave amplitude below the still water level. The threshold can be set by using C_{B1} .

3 USER MANUAL

3.1 Flowchart

The BOSZ model is embedded in a Matlab/Octave environment. The main program file (BOSZ_2D.m) calls a pre-compiled C++ routine (PC.cpp), which contains the entire computation of the time loop. The Matlab/Octave environment is only necessary for preprocessing and loading of input files. The compiled functions can be executed in parallel through OpenMP.

The computation stays within the PC.cpp during the entire computation of the time loop. All data is saved by the C++ routines. Figure 3.1 shows a flow chart of the computational procedure.

Algorithm 1: PC.cpp
<p>All variables from the initial condition are loaded through the MEX interface into the PC.cpp routine.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make temporary arrays; <p>Enter time loop:</p> <p>for <i>time step</i> = 0, 1, 2, 3, ... do</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compute a mask of wet-dry cells (use threshold $H < H_{\min}$); - Compute Δt; - Compute wave input (either at boundary or internally \rightarrow spectral wavemaker); <p>for <i>ORDER</i> = 1 : 2 do</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compute conserved variables H, Hu and Hv, eta, z_a; - Compute spatial derivatives for dispersion terms; - Check for wave breaking (Fr-number or momentum gradient criterion); - Map out cells near dry boundaries; - Map out areas for FV and FD computation (if $FD=1$); - Reconstruct variables at interfaces in the x direction for η, H, and u, v; - Reconstruct variables at interfaces in the y direction for η, H, and v, u; - Compute Riemann solution for all cell interfaces; - Compute fluxes of SWE part (partially in FD and FV); - Compute friction matrix; - Compute continuity dispersion terms (spatial derivatives only); - Compute <i>continuity equation</i> - Compute momentum dispersion terms (spatial derivatives only); - Compute eddy viscosity (only if $eddy > 0$); - Compute <i>momentum equation</i> - Predictor time integration or Corrector time integration; - Solution of TDMA to extract u and v from P and Q; - Apply boundary conditions; <p>end</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compute xyt crossterms for next time step; - Save output files; - Proceed to next time step ; <p>end</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Delete temporary arrays;

Figure 3.1: Wave celerity of [Nwogu, 1993] equations in comparison with the classical Boussinesq equations [Peregrine, 1967].

3.2 User-Defined Input

To run the BOSZ model, an input file with the steering variables is necessary. The user-variable file is the only file that needs to be set up. Besides preparation of bathymetry or wave input files, no other file in the source code has to be changed manually unless the user decides to alter the source code. All variables in USERVARS.m have a short description, but there are a few key variables, which will be highlighted here:

ORDR:

The order of time integration. The user has the option of using a 2nd, 3rd, or 4th order strong stability preserving Runge-Kutta scheme. Usually, the 2nd order scheme is sufficient and it is also the fastest. The higher order schemes are a little less diffusive, and sometimes necessary. Especially, if the flow is very dispersive. But it all comes at extra computational cost.

CFLNum:

The Courant-Friedrichs-Levy number. Usually CFLNum = 0.5 is ok.

INP:

Defines type of input wave. (0) datafile (has to be specified in initial condition), (1) analytical solution such as solitary or sine wave, (2) wave spectrum (can be empirical or from SWAN file). Attention, for sine waves generated inside domain set INP=2 and sinewave=1. A sine wave is treated like a wave spectrum with only one component - monochromatic wave.

realSpec:

empirical wave spectrum (0), or SWAN spectrum (2)

theta2:

directional window of wave spectrum, 180 covers entire offshore spectrum, but the use of a narrower window is recommended to reduce the load on the wavemaker. The user is recommended to inspect the input wave spectrum.

thinc:

number of directional bins (recommended use: thinc = theta2).

theta:

offset of peak wave angle. If 0, then peak direction is centered around 0 (normal to wavemaker).

facT:

ratio of wavelength to water depth, at which input spectrum is truncated. See Figure 2.5 for details.

DLINIT:

The initial wave height of a solitary, sine wave, or significant wave height of a self-made spectrum, such as Bretschneider or TMA. This does not affect the magnitude of a wave spectrum from a SWAN/WWIII spectrum.

Tp:

The peak period of a sine wave or of a self-made spectrum, such as Bretschneider or TMA.

ConW, ConE, ConS, ConN:

Boundary conditions for the left, right, lower, and upper side. The directions refer to the orientation of the matrix with the open ocean side pointing to the left.

TIMEOU:

Total computation time in [sec].

Zalpha:

Reference depth, at which velocities are evaluated. Use default value around -0.53. Careful, solution is very sensitive to small changes!

WL:

Initial water level. Positive numbers add water to the domain, and vice versa. For example, if the computed scenario is focusing on a high tide water level of half a meter above MSL, then $WL = 0.5$. The free surface is then computed around the WL level. The WL value is NOT altering the bathymetry.

FD:

Very useful for long computations where grid diffusion is critical. $FD = 1$ activates a simply Finite Difference upwind scheme and ignores the computationally expensive Finite Volume scheme. The FD scheme uses an upwind flux discretization with a flux limiter for stability. The scheme is computationally very efficient, since it only requires one for-loop instead of the more complex FV scheme with Reconstruction and Riemann solution. The shock capturing capabilities are acceptable but not as good as with the pure FV scheme.

FrBreak:

Defines the type of method used to identify cells where where breaking occurs. (0) used the momentum gradient method with $B = 0.5$, (1) uses the Fr -number criterion with $Cb1$ as the Froude number, (2) uses the wave height to depth ratio with $Cb1$ as the ratio. See Section 2.3.6. for details.

edvis:

Activates the eddy viscosity scheme (no deactivation of dispersion terms in this case).

Hfix:

Uniform depth over entire numerical domain

Mfix, Nfix:

These two values can be used to truncate the bathymetry for quick testing of the model setup. This is very convenient and should be used before every new computation, especially if the domain is large. For example, $Mfix = 1:200$ and $Nfix = 1:300$ reduces the current computational domain to the first 200 cells in longshore direction (along the wavemaker) and 300 cells in cross-shore direction (normal to the wavemaker). Of course, the input grid has to be larger or equal in size compared to the specified $Mfix$, $Nfix$ dimensions. Simple 1D tests can be conducted by selecting only 1 column of a 2D bathymetry. This is particularly useful to check the input wave conditions. Use $Mfix$ and set it to any number smaller or equal to the amount of grid cells in y -direction (direction along wavemaker), e.g. $Mfix = 1$ or $Mfix = 379$.

DXfix, DYfix:

Grid size dimensions for self-defined bathymetry. The grid size of an input bathymetry cannot be changed, but it is possible to design an input matrix of constant depth, dimension, and grid spacing. In this case, the name of the input bathymetry in gridfile must not exist, e.g. gridfile = Oahu.mat3. The .mat3 -ending does not exist, so no file is loaded. Then, a new bathymetry of constant depth $Hfix$, dimensions $Mfix$, $Nfix$,

and resolution DXfix, Dyfix can be designed. This is an easy way of checking the propagation direction of a directional wave spectrum.

The following example produces a bathymetry of uniform 50m depth that is 300 grid cells wide (y-direction, longshore) and 500 cells long (x-direction, cross-shore). The grid resolution cross-shore is 5m (DXfix) and 7m (DYfix) in longshore along the wavemaker trajectory. Given this resolution, the domain is 2500m in cross-shore and 2100m in longshore. Keep in mind to set the bathymetry file name to some non-existing extension such as gridfile = nofile.abc, or similar endings.

3.3 Running the Model

BOSZ can be executed in the non-commercial GNU Octave or the commercial Matlab environment. The code has been run successfully on Linux, Windows, and Mac operating systems. The computationally expensive part of the code is running in pre-compiled C++ scripts, which are embedded in the Octave/Matlab environment. The Octave/Matlab files are mainly for computation of the initial condition, saving of output data, and optional plotting of the result. No specific Matlab toolbox is required as all computational effort of the model is done in C++.

Compilation of the C++ routines (stored in the C_routines folder) requires a functional compiler being linked through the Octave/Matlab interface. Most versions come already with a compiler suite. The GNU gcc/g++ package, which is commonly installed on Linux machines, is recommended. The PC.cpp routine can utilize multiple processing cores through OpenMP.

It is necessary to install Matlab or Octave to run the model. Octave is a free version of Matlab. The installation usually requires additional libraries to successfully link the software with the GNU compilers. Besides the GNU gcc/g++ compiler packages, it is recommended to install “liboctave-dev” through “sudo apt-get install liboctave-dev”.

Test runs conducted for the development of the model presented in this report were performed in Matlab 2007, 2009, 2010, 2011, 2013, 2014, and 2016 with standard gcc compilers linked through the Matlab GUI on Linux machines. The code was also executed in Octave-3.8.1 on a MacBook Pro 10.9.5 and in Octave-4.0.1 on a Linux workstation. The compiler linkage in the Microsoft Windows environment might be slightly different; however, the code has been run on several Windows machines before. With the computing environment verified, BOSZ can be launched from the conventional Matlab GUI by simply executing the main file BOSZ_2D.m. Alternatively, the program can be run in a command terminal (typical on Mac and Linux machines) without graphic output or GUI by invoking: “matlab -nodisplay -nodesktop -nojvm -nosplash -r BOSZ_2D”.

In Octave, simply invoke the program from the terminal via: “octave BOSZ_2D.m”.

Once the model is initiated by running the main file BOSZ_2D.m, the user-defined variables are loaded, the C-routines are compiled, and the initial condition is set up. For spectral waves such as defined by a SWAN spectrum or by an empirical spectrum (e.g. JONSWAP), this includes pre-processing of the spectral wave input and the wavemaker source function.

3.4 Case Study: Monochromatic Wave Propagation over Submerged Bar

[Beji & Battjes, 1993] described a series of laboratory experiments to investigate wave propagation over a submerged bar. The test uses a monochromatic wave of 1 cm wave amplitude and 2.02s period. Figure 3.2 shows a schematic of the 37.7m long, 0.8m wide, and 0.75m high flume with a 0.3m high trapezoidal bar at 6m from a piston-type wavemaker. The bar has a 1:20 front slope followed by a 2m flat crest and a 1:10 back slope. A gravel beach at the end of the flume acts as a wave absorber. Waves shoal when propagating up the slope of the bar forcing development of bound higher harmonics, which are then released from the carrier frequency on the lee side of the bar as the water depth parameter kh increases rapidly (where k is the wave number). Sand bars are quite common in coastal waters making this experiment an important test case for nearshore models. Many Boussinesq-type or non-hydrostatic models do not fully resolve the higher harmonics due to low-order approximation of nonlinearity and dispersion in the governing equations.

The input files are called USERVARS_barA.m in combination with the bathymetry file bargrid_002.mat at 2 cm resolution. The input wave is a sinusoidal wave based on an analytical solution that is placed near the left boundary behind the sponge layer. The wavemaker then generates the wave symmetrically in both direction, of which the outgoing waves are fully absorbed by the sponge layer. With an internal wavemaker, outgoing and reflected waves can cross the source area and leave the domain. This generation/absorption is close to an open ocean boundary condition. The USERVARS_barA.m file contains the grid indices where the time series of the free surface elevation are recorded.

The important variables in the USERVARS file are:

- DLINIT = 0.0205; (wave height)
- Tp = 2.02; (wave period)
- INP = 2 ;(for oscillatory waves)
- sinewave = 1; (monochromatic wave)
- TIMEOU = 50; (total computation time)
- tprintXY = 0.02; (output time interval at wave gauges)
- CoX = [725;825;875;925;985;1065;1150;1250]; (location of wave gauges in x-direction)
- CoY = [1;1;1;1;1;1;1]; (location of wave gauges in y-direction)
- ConW = 2; (left boundary condition: sponge layer)
- ConE = 2; (right boundary condition: sponge layer)

Figure 3.2: Definition sketch of wave transformation over a submerged bar. (a) Laboratory setup from [Beji & Battjes, 1993]. (b) Numerical model setup. Numbered circles denote wave gauge locations.

Figure 3.3 shows the comparison between the computed free surface elevation and the observed signals at the respective gauge locations. Overall, the model is in good agreement with the data. The evolution of the free surface elevation includes all major processes such as shoaling and the generation of super-harmonics. These high frequency waves are locally larger than $kh = \pi$ and therefore beyond the ideal application range of the model. Nevertheless, the model provides reasonable results even for conditions.

Figure 3.3: Results from BOSZ for [Beji & Battjes, 1993] test. Numerical computations in blue line. Circles denote the recorded wave form at the wave gauge locations.

REFERENCES

[Beji & Battjes, 1993]	Beji, S. and Battjes, J. Experimental investigation of wave propagation over a bar. Coastal Engineering, 19(1-2):151–162. Dated 1993.
[Gottlieb & Shu, 1998]	Gottlieb, S. and Shu, C.-W. Total Variation Diminishing Runge-Kutta Schemes. Math. Comput. Dated 1998.
[Grant Agreement, 2018]	Grant Agreement number: 763959 — MegaRoller — H2020-LCE-2016-2017/H2020-LCE-2017-RES-RIA-TwoStage Dated 26/03/2018.
[Kim, et al. 2008]	Kim, S., Lee, S., and Kim, K. H. Wavenumber-extended high-order oscillation control finite volume schemes for multi-dimensional aeroacoustic computations. Journal of Computational Physics, 227(8):4089–4122 Dated 2008.
[Nwogu, 1993]	Nwogu, O. An alternative form of the Boussinesq equations for nearshore wave propagation. Journal of Waterway, Port, Coastal, and Ocean Engineering. Dated 1993.
[Peregrine, 1967]	Peregrine, D.H. Long waves on a beach. Journal of Fluid Mechanics. Dated 1967.
[Toro, 2001]	Toro, E.F. Shock-capturing methods for free-surface shallow flows. John Wiley and Sons. Dated 2001.
[Wei, 1999]	Wei, G., Kirby, J. T., and Sinha, A. Generation of waves in Boussinesq models using a source function method. Coastal Engineering. Dated 1999.